

Guardian Rover: Advanced Night Surveillance for Women's Safety and Monitoring

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Abstract: In many places of the world these days, women's safety is the first priority. Therefore, everyone in the society wants a safe and secure system in place. The safety electronic system for women's safety is the subject of our study. In this project, we utilize openCV and a raspberry pi to enable night vision on a security camera. This is an inexpensive approach that makes use of a Raspberry Pi camera and a chip the size of a credit card. CNN, a deep learning method, is employed in anomaly detection. Thus, the picture is taken with the Pi camera and sent to the Raspberry Pi for openCV-assisted face and human detection processing. With the help of an application programming interface called Twilio, this is further delivered to the authorized user along with the crime scene location. Additionally, the authorized user receives a mail attachment with a photograph of that unique circumstance. The accuracy of this approach is roughly 83%. We have developed a system that can record events and identify anomalous activity with the aid of a smart surveillance system.

Keywords: Raspberry Pi, Raspberry Pi camera, Convolutional Neural Network(CNN), OpenCV , Twilio.

1. Introduction

People's only want in life these days is to feel protected and secure. The CCTV is the security system that is most frequently employed. The size and usage of the system determine how much it will cost to install CCTV. Typically, public spaces like parking lots, malls, and hospitals are where it is deployed. On the other hand, CCTV allows for round-the-clock area monitoring and the retrieval of recorded video material as needed. It enables the police to locate and investigate crimes and can be used to detect criminality. An essential resource for many businesses and homeowners is security. Additionally, it prevents harm to people and the loss or theft of personal property. Each year, companies and homeowners set aside a large budget only for security measures. On average a security guard's annual salary is around \$25,000. It expense increases with the number of alarm systems, surveillance cameras and hired security guards. In 2011 homeowners spent about \$20.64 billion on united state home security systems.

These figures demonstrate how important safety is to both businesses and private citizens. With the aid of a Raspberry Pi 3 and a Pi camera designed specifically for the device, we have developed a smart system that offers both face detection and face recognition. Additionally, an IR sensor has been linked to detect obstacles, and a sound sensor is utilized to identify any strange sounds. As soon as there is any anomalous activity or sound, the camera opens and records a picture of the scene. Using an application programming interface called Twilio, this is further delivered to the authorized user together with the location of the crime scene. If any weapons are identified, the system will also send a photograph of the intruder to the authorized user via mail. And in response, more steps can be done.

2. Proposed System

Fig. 1. Functional block diagram

The proposed system, Raspberry pi is installed with the night vision camera that helps the system find the intruders and go for the automation. The robot covers a specific area and checks for any intruders when an intruder or weapon is detected, the owner is alerted by the buzzer sound. We propose a robot patrolling security which uses night vision camera to secure any premises. The robotic vehicle moves at specific intervals, and is equipped

with camera and sound sensors for night vision. In patrolling it uses a predefined line to follow its path. It stops at specific points and if sound is detected moves to next points. To patrol assigned area, the system uses IR-based path following system. It monitors each area using 360degree rotating HD camera to detect any intrusion. It is capable of tracking sound at the premises. Any sound after company is closed and its predefined path begins to move towards the sound. It then scans the area using its camera to detect any identified human faces It captures and begins to transmit images of the situation immediately upon detection of sound or human face.

A. Raspberry Pi 3

Fig. 2. Raspberry pi diagram

The Raspberry Pi foundation created the Raspberry Pi, a tiny single-board computer, in the UK with the goal of advancing computer science education in both developed and poor nations. Outside of its intended market, the original model outsold the projected sealing in terms of popularity, particularly for robotic applications. The Pi 3 Model B+ has a processor speed range of 700 MHz to 1.4 GHz and on-board memory that spans from 256 MB to 1 GB RAM..

B. Night Vision Camera

Fig. 3. Raspberry pi 3 Camera module

All Raspberry Pi versions are compatible with this high-definition camera module. offers very tiny and light design, great sensitivity, reduced crosstalk, and low noise picture capturing. Through the use of a CSI connection made especially for connecting to cameras, the camera module is connected to the Raspberry Pi board. The CSI bus just sends pixel data to the CPU and can handle very high data speeds..

C. DC Motor

Fig. 4. DC motor

One type of rotating electrical machine that transforms electrical direct current into mechanical energy is the DC motor. The forces generated determine which magnetic field kinds are more dependent on. Almost all varieties of DC motors contain an internal mechanism, whether electromechanical or electronic, that allows them to periodically change the direction of the current flowing through a portion of the motor. Due to their ability to draw power from the direct current lighting distribution networks already in place, DC motors were the first to be employed extensively. A DC motor's speed may be varied widely by varying the current force in its field windings or by employing a variable supply voltage. Toys, appliances, and tools all employ small DC motors..

D. IR Sensor

Fig. 5. Infrared sensor

The operational infrared sight and programmed control choices are utilized by the IR infrared sensor module. It has low power consumption, low voltage work mode, excellent reliability, and flexible sensitivity. Typically included into different electrical devices for automatic detection, particularly in battery-operated and preprogrammed control systems.

E. Sound Sensor

Fig. 6. Sound sensor

A sound sensor is a device that uses sound intensity to identify and translate sound waves into electrical signals.

Let's first have a look at the sound sensor module that will be used in this tutorial before moving on to how to integrate a sound sensor with Arduino. The Grove sound sensor module, which is built on the LM386 power amplifier, is an easy-to-use, low-power, and highly compatible alternative for getting your next sound detecting project off to a quick start. The potentiometer's adjustable output and wide voltage range enable it to determine the level of background noise with ease.

F. H-Bridge

Dual H-bridge Motor Driver Integrated Circuit (IC): An H-bridge circuit is one that permits voltage to flow in either direction. Large, silent motors can also be driven by the L293D; see the Voltage Specification at the end. It operates on the H-bridge idea.. As we know voltage need to change

H-bridge integrated circuits are perfect for operating DC motors because, as we all know, voltage must change direction in order to rotate a motor in either a clockwise or counterclockwise manner. Two separate h-Bridge circuits that can rotate two DC motors are present on a single L293D chip. Because of its small size, it is often utilized in robotic applications to regulate DC motors. The pin diagram for an L293D motor controller is shown below..

G. Power Supply

One piece of hardware that gives electricity to an electrical equipment is called a power supply. It takes input from an outlet and changes the current from alternating current (AC) to direct current (DC), which is what the gadget requires. Additionally, it regulates the voltage to a safe level, enabling the gadget to function without overheating. Any computer's power source is a crucial component that has to function correctly for the other parts to function. To discover the power supply on a system unit, just locate the input where the power cord is plugged in.

H. Wi-Fi Module

It makes use of a 32-bit RISC CPU based on the Tensilica Xtensa L106, which runs at 80 MHz (or 160 MHz when overclocked). It contains 64 KB of boot ROM, 64 KB of RAM instructions, and 96 KB of RAM data. SPI allows for the access of external flash memory. One inexpensive standalone wireless transceiver that may be used to create Internet of Things endpoints is the ESP8266 module. A series of AT instructions must be used by the microcontroller in order to connect with the ESP8266 module. The microcontroller connects with the ESP8266-01 module at a defined Baud rate via UART. Numerous independent producers create various modules utilizing this chip..

I. Twilio

Product engineers may use the Twilio application to do many communication functions via its online management APIs, as well as automatically make and receive calls, send and receive instant messages, and more..

3. Literature Review

1. Published in 2017: "Implementation of spy robot for surveillance system using internet protocol of Raspberry pi" was published in 2017. Abdalla, Ghanem Osman Elhaj. Recent developments in electronics, information, and communication technology (RTEICT) is the subject of the second IEEE International Conference. Currently, maintaining monitoring over international borders is a challenging undertaking. Although the border is being closely monitored by the border protecting personnel, this cannot be done constantly. A robot that can autonomously identify trespassers at the border and notify the nearest board security control unit is a crucial necessity in this scenario. Nowadays, a lot of military branches use robots to complete dangerous tasks that people are unable to complete. In the current effort. The sensors and night vision pi camera make up the spy robot system. Users receive information on the PIR sensor's ability to identify live things via the web server, and the pi camera simultaneously records moving items for posting on the webpage. Wheel drive control buttons on the webpage allow

the user in the control room to access the robot. Robots can also be programmed to move automatically by using obstacle-detecting sensors to prevent collisions. This spy robot surveillance system may be tailored for use in a variety of settings, including banks, retail centers, and businesses. "Review of human detection techniques in night vision" was published in 2018. The WiSPNET is an international conference on wireless communications, signal processing, and networking, organized by Sonu Kumar Sharma of the CSE department of MNNIT in Allahbad. In many computer vision automations, human identification has never been easy. When human detection occurs in a nighttime scenario, the significance of this issue increases. One such use where a night vision device is absolutely necessary is surveillance. An automated system that uses night vision to detect people might be a useful tool for monitoring in any sensitive areas. In this article, two algorithms for identifying people in night vision footage were studied. The background subtraction approach employs the difference picture derived from the input image and a created background image, whereas the proposed hot-spot algorithm makes use of black body radiation theory. The experiments conducted using these methodologies are analyzed in terms of their results..

2. Published in 2017: "Robotman: An Interaction Robot for Human-Robot Security" 18th International Conference on Advance Robotics (ICAR), Alexander Lopez The concept, development, and first testing of Robotman—a robot with capabilities for both human-to-human interaction and security patrolling—are presented in this study. The robot is based on data that was gathered from a security business, whose employees are required to engage with the public and provide extra information about the region they watch in addition to performing security patrol duties. During the day, the robot may serve as a guide, and at night, it can conduct security patrols. In order to patrol broad interior spaces, engage with people, greet, inform, and direct customers to their destination, as well as serve as a telepresence platform for the human security officers, we created and constructed a sturdy, easily assembled, anthropomorphic security robot. Our findings imply that Robot Man is a person-friendly and aesthetically beautiful robot that can engage with people and carry out security-related duties.

3. Published in 2019: "Depth Image-Based Indoor Patrol Robot Obstacle Avoidance" Zhenghan Jiang, International Conference on Cybernetics and Machine Learning, 2019 (ICMLC). For many years, researchers have researched image-based obstacle avoidance. The fact that performance of image-based methods typically depends on illumination conditions is one of their weaknesses. That is to say, in dimly lit areas, performance may be quite subpar. In this study, we explore the viability of using a depth image-based strategy for indoor patrolling that is done full-time. We start by taking a look at a three-class issue. Every depth picture is categorized as "normal" if there are no obstacles nearby, as "notice" if there are obstacles close, and as "danger" if there are none. An well-trained convolutional neural network called AlexNet is utilized for classification. It is retrained using transfer learning, and the label of each depth picture is determined based on the RGB image taken concurrently.

In the University of Aizu's Research Quadrangle, we gathered 102,776 picture data for our main experiment. The test findings demonstrate that the depth image-based strategy performs well in both day and night conditions, and in most circumstances, it outperforms the RGB image-based approach. When creating more useful full-time patrol robots, this outcome may offer fresh perspectives.

4. Design and Implementation

1) Flow chart of creating database

The flowchart below shows the steps involved in creating an authorized user database:

Fig. 7. Flow chart of creating database

The pi camera in front of the robot begins to record the user's face as soon as it obtains electricity. In order to facilitate face detection, it takes the set of photos and saves them in a user reference database for authentication. Thirty to fifty photos will make up that authorized user database in order to achieve high precision in face identification and prevent the discovery of unauthorized faces as permitted. The picture database generated by the authorized individual is transformed into matrix format for quicker and more precise detection.

2) Flowchart for face detection and authentication

The flow-chart below shows the entire Security Patrolling Robot operation:

Fig. 8. Flow chart of face detection and authentication

When the robot is first started, the camera recognizes the face in front of it and compares it to a reference database. The collected face is routed to the training sequence, where it undergoes matrix translation and is cross-referenced with the current reference database. If the face is verified, the robot advances and begins to continually check. The owner is alerted by the buzzer going off if the face cannot be verified.

3) Flow diagram of unusual activity detection system using CNN

- Pi Camera is used to acquire images by capturing picture frames.
- Haar cascade classifiers are used to recognize people and objects in pictures.
- Gaussian blurring is used.
- Canny Edge detector: an edge detecting tool.
- An abnormal act is now looked for in this preprocessed picture.

CNN Segment:

- The COCO dataset is used to extract images with labels.
- If the CNN model finds evidence of a weapon or questionable behavior, it alerts the designated user.

Fig. 9. Flow diagram of unusual activity detection system

5. Result

The worrying rise in crime is one way that the smart surveillance camera effectively reduces threats to security. With the use of an implemented algorithm akin to a cascade—a Haar classifier—it is easy to identify a human face. Subsequent CNN models or algorithms are designed to identify atypical or criminally motivated activity. Additionally, if any unexpected sounds are heard, such shouting or someone begging for aid, a picture of the scenario is taken and transmitted to the authorized user. No notification is sent if there is no indication of criminal intent. The SMS module will activate and deliver it to the user with the help of the Twilio application if any individual is spotted using abnormal behavior or a weapon.

A. Normal Activity

No notification is sent if there is no indication of criminal intent..

Fig. 10. No crime

B. Suspicious Activity

Should someone be found to be using a weapon or exhibiting unusual behavior, the SMS module will initiate and notify the user..

Fig. 11. Crime detected

6. Conclusion and Future Scope

In this study, we have suggested CNN, a deep learning method, to identify weapons and anomalous activities. The job of this nighttime roaming surveillance rover is to keep an eye out for threats and to provide continuous monitoring. Swarm robotics can be used in future work to deploy many robots and cover greater regions.

There are several applications for this technology in a variety of industries, including banking and forensics. This system's great degree of compactness and ability to distinguish faces and send an email alert instantly explain why it's rather handy. In addition to this face recognition can also

Furthermore, facial recognition technology may be used in the future. The foundation of any security system is recognition. A well-trained database is often necessary for the finest recognition system, since it serves as the foundation for our recognition. Therefore, in order to access the database, you must first gather the subject's photo for identification. We can offer facial recognition after we have our system and have trained it. Regarding the potential applications of this technology and the protection of women, this robot can serve as a helper and a good samaritan. Swarm robotics can be used in future work to deploy many robots and cover greater regions.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the reviewers for their insightful recommendations and criticism, which have helped to elevate the work. We are grateful to our institution for enabling us to complete our project there. We humbly and sincerely appreciate our department for any assistance that they have provided.

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